

Volume 02 Issue 01
Jan-Jun 2026

*Corresponding
Author:-
ooluwaseyi@unimed.
edu.ng

Submission Date: Nov, 03,
2025

Copyright Date : Nov, 20,
2025

Awareness and Knowledge of Rhesus-D Incompatibility among Young Adults in Federal College of Agriculture Akure Ondo State

Oluwaseyi O.T.^{1}, Alasoluyi M.O.¹*

*Faculty of Nursing Science, Department of Maternal and
Child Health Nursing Sciences, University of Medical
Sciences, Akure Campus, Ondo State, Nigeria*

ABSTRACT

Background: *Rhesus-D incompatibility is a condition with much medical concern; this study presents an opportunity for young adults to be assessed about the predisposition and complications of rhesus-D incompatibility.*

Aim: *The purpose of this study was to assess the awareness and knowledge of rhesus-d incompatibility among young adults.*

Methods: *The awareness and understanding of rhesus-d incompatibility among 101 respondents chosen using multistage sample approaches was evaluated using a cross-sectional descriptive survey design. Data for the study was gathered using a self-structured questionnaire (Cronbach value = 0.82), and SPSS software version 23 was utilized for analysis.*

Results: *Findings revealed 58% of the respondents are between the age of 16-20 years. Also, 65% of the young adults were female while 36% are male. Only 83% of young adults know their blood group. However, only 28% indicated that they know their family members blood group. Finding this study shows that a substantial number of respondents have heard about rhesus-D incompatibility but do not have adequate information on the causes, effect and its prevention. Also, about two-third 64% agree that Rhesus-D incompatibility is preventable. In addition, no significant difference was found between the knowledge of Rhesus-D incompatibility based on the respondents' gender, $t(98) = 1.383, p = 0.960$ at $P < 0.05$ level of significant.*

Conclusion: *Based on the finding recommendation were put forward among that, nurses should intensify information dissemination on Rhesus-D incompatibility among young adult through sensitization programs.*

Keywords: *Awareness, knowledge, rhesus-d incompatibility, young adults*

INTRODUCTION

Rhesus-D incompatibility is a medical condition that is determined by the presences or absence of the Rhesus-D antigen. This Rhesus-D antigen or protein belongs to the human blood group system and is prioritized second after the ABO blood group, although, they are both inherited from individual's parent [1]. This rhesus protein could be either positive (represents the presence of the D-antigen) or negative (represents the absence of the D-antigen). Rhesus-D incompatibility occurs as a result of exposure of a rhesus negative mother to a rhesus positive fetal blood, can cause the child to develop hemolytic illness by releasing Rh-antibodies that cross the placenta and kill the fetal red blood cell. [2]. Sequel to this, Rh-negative mother has increased chances of developing sensitivity to Rh antigen especially if it occurs during delivery or other medical procedures such as transfusion [3]. According to the World Health Organization, rhesus-D incompatibility continues to scale as a contributor to perinatal mortality and results in diseases such as hemolytic disease of the fetus and new born which in severe cases could result in fetal anemia with risk of death, severe neonatal hyperbilirubinemia and kernicterus [4]. Rh illness is thought to affect 276 out of every 100,000 live births worldwide, which is significant considering that an estimated 50% of untreated cases of hemolytic disease of the newborn will either die or develop brain damage due to the disease. Because of better prenatal and neonatal care, the prevalence of rhesus disease has decreased to 2.5 per 100,000 live births in developed nations. [5]. Although, the introduction of Rh-D immune globulin at around the 26th to 28th week of pregnancy, after abortion and within 72hrs of delivery has significantly reduced the occurrence of maternal sensitization from 13.2% to 0.2% [6].

One way to effectively control and prevent negative outcomes is for individuals to be aware of their Rh blood group status. The results of this investigation demonstrate antigen mismatch. Young adulthood is a critical window period that presents opportunities and challenges for improving health. Health at this age can affect health throughout the lifespan. Determination of Rhesus-D blood group allows reasonable precautions that limit the risk to the fetus [4]. Despite the availability of screening, very few people are aware of blood types, Rh incompatibility, prevention, and associated complications during pregnancy and after childbirth. Yet studies reviewed show that in developing countries like Nigeria, knowledge is considerably lower as it is a rare and under discussed topic. Many people are ignorant of blood types, the rhesus factor, and the problems associated with Rhesus-D incompatibility for mothers and their offspring. [7].

According to a study conducted by Kukasalan and Oner [8] on knowledge, attitude and behaviors of pregnant women on screening test made during pregnancy it was found that majority were aware about rhesus incompatibility, also, Abie et al. [9] revealed that only few of the respondent had knowledge on rhesus-D incompatibility and claim they would seek help in case of stillbirths or miscarriage. A cross sectional study conducted by Aljuhaysh et al [10] on Maternal-fetal Rhesus (Rh) factor incompatibility in Arar, only 38% of the mothers in northern Saudi Arabia were aware of Rh (D) incompatibility, 68.5% were aware of anti-D immunoglobulin, and 51% were aware of when anti-D immunoglobulin should be administered.

Oyeyemi et al. [11] study on knowledge of sickle cell and rhesus factor incompatibility in the university of Ilorin reported only 19.5% had a high level of rhesus factor incompatibility knowledge. Furthermore, Ojo and Osuntusa [7] reported a fair

knowledge of rhesus factor and incompatibility but a poor aware of the importance of taking the test and the complications it posed was identified. Furthermore, Yahia et al.'s study [12] on Blood Group Rhesus-D-Negativity and Awareness toward the Importance of Anti-D Immunoglobulin among Pregnant Women in Bisha, Saudi Arabia, found that 68.5% of pregnant women knew about anti-D immunoglobulin, and 51% knew when it should be administered. Ahmad and Banan (2022) [13] reported that majority of the respondents did not know their blood group not to mention their rhesus factor, this shows a lack of awareness towards the whole topic. Hence, this study aims to assess the awareness and knowledge on Rhesus-D incompatibility among young adults in Federal College of Agriculture, Akure.

Research Question

- What is the awareness of Rhesus-D incompatibility among young adults in Federal College of Agriculture, Akure?
- What is the knowledge of Rhesus Factor among young adults in Federal College of Agriculture, Akure?
- What is the knowledge of Rhesus-D incompatibility prevention among young adults in Federal College of Agriculture, Akure?

Research Hypothesis

- There is no significant difference between gender and knowledge of rhesus-D incompatibility.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

A descriptive research design was adopted to achieve the aim of this study.

Research Setting

Federal College of Agriculture, Akure is a federal government owned tertiary institution located in Akure, the capital city of Ondo State in Southwestern Nigeria, with coordinates 7.2648N and 5.2313E. The institution was established on 10th January 1957, to develop the agricultural sector by training middle level manpower who will help address the agricultural gap in the state and in the country by extension. The institution which first started as a School of Agriculture, has been accredited by the National Board of Technical Education (NBTE) to award National Diplomas (ND) and Higher National Diplomas in Agricultural related courses.

The school is headed by a provost and other departmental HOD'S in the following departments Animal health and production, Agricultural Technology, Crop Production, Agricultural and Extension Management, Agriculture and Bio-environmental Engineering, Horticulture and Landscape Management, Fishery Technology, Forestry, Agronomy, Pasture and Range Management. The aforementioned departments run both ordinary diploma and higher national diploma (OND & HND).

Sample Size and Population

The target population were students of the department of Crop Production, Horticulture and Landscape Management and Agricultural and Bioenvironmental Engineering at Federal College Agriculture, Akure.

Table 1: Total population of students in each department.

Department	OND 1	OND 2	HND1	HND2	Total
Horticulture and Landscape Management	0	2	7	5	14
Crop Production	15	20	11	11	57
Agriculture and Bioenvironmental Engineering	20	15	17	12	64
Total					135

Using the Taro Yamane's formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

N = 135 students across the three selected department

e = 0.05 margin of error

n= 101 students as sample size

Sampling Technique

Multistage sampling method was used to recruit a total of 101 respondents for the study. In the first stage the faculties were divided. In the second stage, each faculty was sub-divided into departments. In the third stage, three department was selected randomly which were Crop Production, Horticulture and Landscape Management and Agriculture and Bio-environmental Engineering among the department. In the fourth stage, convenience sampling was used to select eligible and consenting students who were willing to fill in the questionnaire.

Data Instrument

A structured questionnaire was developed based on literature reviewed. It was divided into four parts. **Section A:** contains socio-demographic characteristics of the respondent which include age, sex, religion, tribe, department and educational level. **Section B:** contain instrument for measuring awareness about Rhesus-D incompatibility which consists of 8 items. **Section C:** contain instrument for measuring knowledge of Rhesus Factor which consists of 7 items. **Section D:** contain instrument for measuring knowledge of Rhesus-D incompatibility prevention which consists of 6 items. A total of 27 test items to be answered with either True or False and Yes or No. Correct answers were scored '1' and Incorrect answer '0'.

Validity and Reliability

Face and content validity was done to ensure questionnaire was clear, relevant and easy to comprehend by the respondent. A pilot was carried out to test the consistency of the questionnaire using the Cronbach alpha test, a value of 0.82 was confirmed.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics presented in frequency tables, percentages and bar chart on Statistical Package for Social Sciences Version 25.0. The hypotheses were tested with T-test and the level of statistical significance was set at < 0.05.

Ethical consideration

A letter of approval was obtained from the central office for research and development 'of the University of Medical Sciences, for ethical clearance before the commencement of data collection. All participants were fully informed of the objectives and design of the study. Informed consent was obtained from the participants after adequate explanation and information was given to them.

RESULTS

Sociodemographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 2 revealed the respondent demographic variables. From the table it

was observed that 58% of the respondents are between the age of 16-20 years. Also, 65% of the young adults were female while 36% are male. This implies that female young adult constitutes the larger population of the study. In addition, the finding reveals that 86% practice Christianity while 14% practice Islam

religion. On the tribe of the respondents, it was observed that 90% are from Yoruba tribe, 7% Igbo while 3% are from Hausa tribe. In addition, on the educational level of the respondents, observation reveals that 32% of the respondents are in ND II, 27% HNDI and 25% are in HND II while 16% are in NDI 18%.

Table 2: Sociodemographic characteristics of respondents.

Demographic Characteristic of the Respondents	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Age		
16-20 yrs	58	58.0
21-25 yrs	33	33.0
≥ 26yrs	9	9.0
Gender		
Male	36	36.0
Female	65	65.0
Religion Affiliation		
Christianity	86	86.0
Islam	14	14.0
Tribe		
Yoruba	90	90.0
Igbo	7	7.0
Hausa	3	3.0
Level		
ND1	16	16.0
ND2	32	32.0
HND1	27	27.0
HND2	25	25.0

Awareness of Rhesus-D Incompatibility among Young Adults

Table 3 revealed that 71% of the respondents were aware of Rhesus-D incompatibility, 28% indicated that they do not aware while only 1% don't know that there is Rhesus-D incompatibility. Also, 48% were aware that rhesus-D incompatibility can affect a pregnancy and 46% indicated rhesus-D incompatibility may not be as a result of different rhesus blood group of the partner. In addition, 42% were aware that Rhesus-D incompatibility can have devastating effect in a woman during pregnancy and delivery, Majority

(60%) of the young adult are aware of Rhesus-D incompatibility test. More importantly, the respondents (70%) are aware of the need to inject a rhesus-D negative pregnant mother with Rhogam. This means that a substantial amount of respondents have heard about Rhesus-D incompatibility but do not have adequate information on the causes, effects and prevention. Also, **figure 1** shows that 83% indicated that they know their blood group status and 15% do not know their blood group. However, only 28% indicated that they know their family members blood group.

Fig. 1: Awareness of blood group status.

Table 3: Awareness of Rhesus-D incompatibility among young adults.

Awareness of Rhesus-D incompatibility among young adults	Yes (%)	No (%)	I don't Know (%)
Aware of Rhesus-D incompatibility	71(71.0)	28(28.0)	1(1.0)
Aware that Rhesus-D incompatibility can affect a pregnancy	48(48.0)	46(46.0)	6(6.0)
Rhesus-D incompatibility may not be as a result of different rhesus blood group of your partner	46(46.0)	44(44.0)	10(10.0)
I am aware Rhesus-D incompatibility can have devastating effect in a woman during pregnancy and delivery	42(42.0)	30(30.0)	28(28.0)
Aware of Rhesus-D incompatibility test	62(60.0)	34(34.0)	6(6.0)
Aware of the need to inject a Rhesus-D negative pregnant mother with Rhogam	70(70.0)	18(18.0)	12(12.0)

Knowledge of Rhesus Factor among Young Adults

Table 4 revealed that 79% ranked true while 21% ranked false that rhesus factor is not an antibody found on the red blood cells. Majority (71%) indicated that it is true that rhesus factor is associated with blood group while 29% indicated it is false. If I have the antibody, I am rhesus negative

showed 57% indicate true. In addition, more than three-quarter 76% indicated that rhesus factor investigations should be done before marriage. In addition, 88% of the respondents indicated that Rhesus factor is inherited from parents while 12% indicated that is false. More than half (67%) agree that there is a difference between blood group and blood genotype.

Table 4: Knowledge of Rhesus Factor among Young Adults.

Knowledge of Rhesus Factor	True (%)	False (%)
Rhesus factor is not an antigen found on the red blood cells.	79(79.0)	21(21.0)
Rhesus factor is associated with blood group.	71(71.0)	29(29.0)
If I have the antigen, I am negative.	57(57.0)	43(43.0)
If I do not have the antigen, I am rhesus positive.	85(85.0)	15(15.0)
Rhesus factor investigations should be done before marriage	76(76.0)	24(24.0)
Rhesus factor is inherited from parents	88(88.0)	12(12.0)
There is a difference between blood group and blood genotype	67(67.0)	33(33.0)

Knowledge of Rhesus-D incompatibility Prevention among Young Adults

Table 5 revealed that less than half (46%) indicated that it is true that the first pregnancy in a Rhesus-D negative mother is safe. This implies that majority of young adults don't have clear knowledge if first pregnancy in a Rhesus-D negative mother is safe. Also, Rhesus-D incompatibility cannot lead to the death of a baby inside the mother's womb as 46% indicated true. In

addition, 64% agree that Rhesus-D incompatibility is preventable. This shows they know that Rhesus-D incompatibility is preventable. Majority 83% agree that fetal blood compatibility test is necessary. Also, few (47%) indicated to know the accuracy of when Rhogam injection should be taken. This further shows that their knowledge of when and how many injections to take is very low in order to prevent Rhesus-D incompatibility.

Table 5: Knowledge of Rhesus-D incompatibility Prevention among Young Adults.

Knowledge of Rhesus-D incompatibility Prevention among Young Adults	True (%)	False (%)	I don't know (%)
The first pregnancy in a Rhesus-D negative mother is safe.	46(46.0)	22(22.0)	32(32.0)
Rhesus-D incompatibility cannot lead to death of a baby inside the mother's womb.	46(46.0)	29(29.0)	25(25.0)
Rhesus-D incompatibility is preventable	64(64.0)	19(19.0)	17(17.0)
Fetal blood compatibility test is necessary	83(83.0)	9(9.0)	8(8.0)
Rhogam injection should be taken three times.	47(47.0)	21(21.0)	32(32.0)

Fig. 2: Knowledge of when Rhogam should be administered.

Figure 2 shows that 40 indicated that the injection should be taken immediately after birth, 20 at 40th week of pregnancy, 18 after 2 weeks of delivery and 15 indicated after 28th week of pregnancy while 7 reveals that the injection should be taken in case there is bleeding. **Table 6** revealed that shows that no significant difference was found between the knowledge of Rhesus-D

incompatibility based on the respondents' gender, $t(98) = 1.383$, $p = 0.960$ at $P < 0.05$ level of significant. Male ($\bar{x} = 7.892$, $S.D = 1.429$) knowledge of Rhesus-D incompatibility is not different from Female ($\bar{x} = 7.484$, $S.D = 1.425$) on the knowled

ge of Rhesus-D incompatibility. Hence, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between male and

female knowledge of Rhesus-D incompatibility was therefore not rejected.

Table 6: *T-test showing difference between male and female student's knowledge of Rhesus-D incompatibility.*

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t	Sig	Decision
Male	37	7.892	1.429	98	1.383	.960	Not Sign. (P<0.05)
Female	65	7.484	1.425				

DISCUSSION

The findings from this study show that more than three-quarter of the respondent were aware of rhesus-D incompatibility which corroborate with the findings from a study by Kukasalan and Oner [8] The majority of study participants had heard of Rh incompatibility, according to an analysis of pregnant women's knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors about screening tests performed during pregnancy.

In addition, most of the respondents are aware of the need to inject a Rhesus-D negative pregnant mother with Rhogam within the appointed periods which supports findings from a cross sectional study conducted by Aljuhaysh et al. [10] on maternal-fetal Rhesus (Rh) factor incompatibility in Arar, northern Saudi Arabia, revealed that just a small percentage of the women under study were aware of Rh (D) incompatibility, and slightly more than half were aware of anti-D immunoglobulin and when to administer it.

Additionally, the majority of respondents were aware of their blood group, whereas just a small percentage said they were aware of a family member's. Similarly, a study done in Nigeria on the pregnant Rhesus negative Nigerian woman by Kotila and Inokpuare [14] where few women were able to tell their husbands blood type, this could be due to the partners curiosity to know their spouse's blood group to help donate incase need arises, or the lack of

knowledge on the usefulness of knowing a partner's blood group.

This study shows that less than half of the respondents knew that presence of antigen meant they are rhesus-D positive. This could be because of their poor exposure to compulsory screening while resuming school. However, this is dissimilar with findings from a study by Ojo and Osuntusa [7] which found out that most of their respondents understood what it meant to be rhesus-D positive or negative.

This study shows that majority understood that about one-third of the respondent knew rhesus-D incompatibility is preventable which disputes findings from research study by Abbie et al [9] only a small percentage of mothers receiving prenatal care at Saint Paul's Hospital Millennium Medical College in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, were aware of the precautions that should be taken to avoid Rh incompatibility, according to an assessment of knowledge, attitude, practice, and related factors regarding Rh incompatibility.

The knowledge on when Rhogam injection should be taken three times, more than two-fifth indicated that it is true. This further shows that their knowledge of when and how many injections to take is very low to prevent Rhesus-D incompatibility. This supports the report from a study by Yahia et al. (2020) [12] where more than half were aware of the time of administration of anti-D immunoglobulin.

IMPLICATION

The study revealed that although many students were aware of rhesus-D incompatibility, their level of knowledge about the condition was inadequate. This finding highlights the need for nurses working in clinical practice, school health, and family health settings to intensify awareness efforts. Furthermore, adequate information about rhesus factor status should be provided to intending couples before marriage or as early as possible. Failure to inform young adults about their rhesus status could have detrimental effects in the future, making education and awareness a critical preventive strategy.

CONCLUSION

In view of findings, the study concluded that young adults' knowledge on rhesus factors and incompatibility needs to be improved through detailed education concerning their blood groups, and what is expected of them. Neonatal death is often associated with complications of rhesus-D incompatibility and hemolytic disease of the new-born posing a serious concern to the healthcare system as a whole. Therefore, strategic interventions aimed at increasing and improving knowledge are vital.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Nurses particularly those in clinical practice, school health, and family health settings, should intensify educational programs on rhesus-D incompatibility.
- Nurses should advocate for and participate in premarital genetic counseling and rhesus factor testing for intending couples.
- Educational institutions should incorporate information about rhesus-D incompatibility into health education curricula to ensure students are informed early about their blood group and rhesus factor.
- Government should implement policy mandating rhesus factor testing during premarital and antenatal care as part of standard reproductive health services.
- Collaboration with other organizations (religious or non-governmental) on sensitization programs to foster awareness on rhesus-D incompatibility.

REFERENCES

1. Louise, M. (2021). *What to know about the Rh factor*. Medical News Today.
2. Leon, S. (2018). *Rhesus incompatibility*. National Library.
3. Al-Kuran, L., Al-Q., R., A.-S., A., A.-A., N., A. S., & A.-K., L. (2023). Distribution of ABO and Rh blood groups among pregnant women attending the obstetrics and gynecology clinic at the Jordan University Hospital. *Scientific Reports*, 13, 13–19.
4. Pegoraro, D., Urbinati, G., Visser, G., Di R. G., Zipursky, A., Stotler, B., & Steven, L. S. (2020). Hemolytic disease of the fetus and newborn due to Rh(D) incompatibility: A preventable disease that still produces significant morbidity and mortality in children. *PLOS ONE*, 15(1), 1–2.
5. Costumbrado, J., Mansour, T., & Ghassemzadeh, S. (2021, December 14). *Rh incompatibility*. StatPearls Publishing.
6. Maruta, M., Tesfaye, K., Birhanu, E., Yigazu, N., Yuya, M., & Mussa, I. (2023). Prevalence and determinants of Rh alloimmunization in Rh-negative women in teaching hospitals of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: A hospital-based cross-sectional study. *Frontiers in Global Women's Health*, 4, 1–9.
7. Ojo, E. A., & Osuntusa, A. O. (2021). Assessment of pregnant women's knowledge and attitude about Rhesus incompatibility prevention at Babcock University Teaching Hospital, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State. *International Journal of Academic Research on Business, Arts and Science*, 3(6), 5–15.

8. Kusaslan, A., & Oner, E. (2018). Examination of the knowledge, attitude and behaviours of pregnant women on screening tests made during pregnancy. *East Journal of Medicine, 23*(2), 84–89.
9. Abbie, M. (2021). *Assessment of knowledge, attitude, practice and associated factors towards Rhesus incompatibility among mothers attending antenatal care at Saint Paul's Hospital Millennium Medical College, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia*. St. Paul's Hospital Millennium Medical College Research Repository.
10. Aljuhaysh, R., El-Fetoh, N., Alanazi, M., Albaqawi, A., Alanazi, W., Alanazi, N., Alanazi, R., Alanazi, A., Alnemer, E., Alenezi, R., Alabdullatif, T. A. A., Alanazi, S., Alanazi, A., & Alsunayni, S. (2017). Maternal–fetal Rhesus (Rh) factor incompatibility in Arar, northern Saudi Arabia. *Electronic Physician, 12*, 5908–5913.
11. Oyeyemi, A., Olushola, O., & Jidda, K. (2022). *Assessment of health education students' knowledge of sickle cell and Rhesus factor incompatibility in the University of Ilorin*.
12. Yahia, A., Miskeen, E., Sohail, S. K., Algak, T., Aljadran, S., & K. (2020). Blood group Rhesus D-negativity and awareness toward importance of anti-D immunoglobulin among pregnant women in Bisha, Saudi Arabia. *Cureus, 12*(2), 1–7.
13. Ahmad, M., & Banan, M. (2022). Analysis and knowledge of blood groups and attitudes toward blood donation in Jordan. *Jordan Medical Journal, 56*(1).
14. Kotila, T., & Inokpuare, C. (2018). The pregnant Rhesus-negative Nigerian woman. *Nigerian Postgraduate Medical Journal, 12*, 305–307.